

Short communication

TWO DIFFERENT COLOUR MORPHS OF *STIRETRUS DECEMGUTTATUS*
(LEPELETIER & SERVILLE, 1828) (HEMIPTERA: HETEROPTERA:
PENTATOMIDAE: ASOPINAE) FEEDING AND MATING AT THE SAME TIME

TORSTEN VAN DER HEYDEN

Immenweide 83, D-22523 Hamburg, Germany
E-mail: tmvdh@web.de

The genus *Stiretrus* Laporte, 1833 belongs to the subfamily Asopinae within the Pentatomidae. It includes eight species. Six of them occur in South America: *S. bifrenatus* Breddin, 1906, *S. cinctellus* Germar, 1839, *S. decastigmus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838), *S. decemguttatus* (Lepeletier & Serville, 1828), *S. erythrocephalus* (Lepeletier & Serville, 1828) and *S. loratus* Germar, 1839. *Stiretrus quinquepunctatus* Germar, 1839 can be found on the island of Hispaniola (Haiti and the Dominican Republic), while *S. anchorago* (Fabricius, 1775) is the only species of the genus which is distributed in North America (United States of America) and Central America (Mexico, Guatemala, El Salvador, Honduras, Nicaragua, Costa Rica, Panama) (Grazia *et al.*, 2015; van der Heyden, 2016).

Stiretrus decemguttatus has been reported from Suriname, Brazil, Peru, Bolivia, Paraguay, Argentina and Uruguay (Grazia *et al.*, 2015). It is an important predator of Chrysomelidae (Coleoptera) (Paleari, 2013). The species is known to be highly polymorphic. After colour patterns of hundreds of adults of *S. decemguttatus* were observed, 17 morphs which show uniform or variegated patterns were classified by Paleari (2013).

On December 2nd, 2017, Oscar C. B. Neto was able to make an interesting observation in his backyard in Benedito Novo, Santa Catarina, Brazil. Two different colour morphs of *S. decemguttatus* could be photographed while they were mating and feeding at the same time (Fig. 1). One specimen was feeding on a larva, while the other one was feeding on an Asopine, probably another colour morph of *S. decemguttatus* or a specimen of *S. erythrocephalus*. Both species have similar blue colour patterns which differ in tibial expansions and median abdominal spine (Thomas, 1992), characters which are not visible in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Mating pair of *Stiretrus decemguttatus* (Lepeletier & Serville, 1828), Benedito Novo, Santa Catarina, Brazil, 02.12.2017. (Photo: Oscar C. B. Neto).

Acknowledgements. I would like to thank Oscar C. B. Neto (Benedito Novo, Santa Catarina, Brazil) for providing me with information about his observation reported in this publication and for the photograph used to illustrate it. Furthermore, I would like to thank Jocélia Grazia and Ricardo Brugnera (Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre, Brazil) for helpful information.

References: Grazia, J., Panizzi, A. R., Greve, C., Schwertner, C. F., Campos, L. A., Garbelotto, T. de A. & Fernandes, J. A. M. (2015). *Stink Bugs (Pentatomidae)*, pp. 681-756. In: Panizzi, A. R. & Grazia, J. (eds.). *True Bugs (Heteroptera) of the Neotropics*. Springer Science+Business Media. Entomology in Focus 2. Dordrecht. 902 pp. Paleari, L. M. (2013). *Revista Brasileira de Entomologia*, 57 (1), 75-83. Thomas, D. B. (1992). *Taxonomic synopsis of the Asopine Pentatomidae (Heteroptera) of the Western Hemisphere*. The Thomas Say Foundation. Entomological Society of America. Lanham. 156 pp. van der Heyden, T. (2016). *Arquivos Entomológicos*, 15, 167-169.

СИМУЛТАНО ПАРЕЊЕ И ИСХРАНА
КОД ДВА МОРФОЛОШКА ТИПА ОБОЈЕНОСТИ
STIRETRUS DECEMGUTTATUS (LEPELETIER & SERVILLE, 1828)
(HEMIPTERA: HETEROPTERA: PENTATOMIDAE: ASOPINAE)

Торстен ван дер Хајден

Извод

Oscar C. V. Neto је 02.12.2017 имао прилику да примети интересантну ситуацију у свом дворишту у месту Бенедито Ново, Санта Катарина, Бразил. Два морфолошка типа обојености врсте *Stiretrus decemguttatus* су фотографисана у току симултаног парења и храњења (Сл. 1). Једна јединка се хранила ларвом, док се друга хранила вероватно другим морфолошким типом врсте *S. decemguttatus* или јединком врсте *S. erythrocephalus*. Обе врсте су слично плаво обојене, а разликује се у деловима тибија и средишњем абдоминалним гребеном (Thomas, 1992), карактери који се не виде на приложеној слици.

Received: February 13th, 2018
Accepted: March 23rd, 2018